

PROCESSING PARAMETERS IN MANUFACTURING BIO-BASED COMPOSITES AND THEIR FINISHING WITH LOW TEMPERATURE CURE POWDER COATING

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ABSTRACT

This study is based on evaluating several environmentally friendly aspects in processing and finishing fibre composites such as low-cost Medium Density Fibre (MDF) boards. These include, introducing sustainable materials to replace currently used toxic formaldehyde based binders and adding value to the composites with solvent-free powder coating with aesthetic finishes. The practicality of using conductive fillers, to enable uniform electrical conductivity on the surface of the panels to achieve uniform surface finish with powder coating is also looked into. This is a relatively new concept in composites to facilitate powder coating. The key properties investigated here in the manufacture of MDF include internal bond strength, modulus of rupture, modulus of elasticity and electrical conductivity.

In finishing of the composites, a low-temperature powder coating formulation is evaluated using a thermal analysis method by Differential Scanning Calorimeter (DSC) to study the cure behaviour of powders during processing.

In both investigations, full factorial design of experiments (DoE) was used as the most significant tool to detect the factors influencing to optimise the processing parameters to maximise the responses. The focus of this project includes mechanisms for preserving the technological knowledge through new business models funded by the NZ government to support the NZ manufacturing sector, for accelerating innovations and commercialization with targeted research into new products and markets.

1. INTRODUCTION

In the recent years, the interest in powder coated MDF panels has rapidly increased. Powder coating can add significant value to these fibreboards through near zero VOC, less hazardous waste than conventional solvent borne liquid coatings and recyclability of the over sprayed paint. Despite the numerous advantages offered by the technology, various issues related to the quality of the final powder coated MDF remain.

Powder coating requires electrostatic attraction of powders to the surface to obtain a uniform thickness of the film [1]. For powder coated MDF, it is necessary to have uniform moisture content throughout the panel, which may prove to be difficult. Moreover, it is known that conventional powder coatings cure around 180-200°C and at this temperature, heat-sensitive surfaces like MDF release moisture which creates shrinkage during curing. Thus, the variability in the surface conductivity related to moisture level, porosity and the heat distortion [2] at high temperatures employed to cure powders could lead to poor adhesion or surface defects. Properties of the coated MDF but also the powder coating itself may influence the quality and aspect of the film.

To achieve the best finish with smooth appearance and good adhesion of the coating on powder coated MDF, three parallel approaches are necessary:

- Modification of the MDF composition to make it more suitable for powder coating
- Development of a low temperature cure powder coating (LTPC)
- Optimizing the processing parameters in manufacturing MDF and the LTPC

The present study focuses on how a design of experiments (DoE) approach can be used to optimise the composition of MDF panels to be coated and the manufacturing process of the powder coating. The practicality of introducing carbon black as conductive filler in the composition of MDF panels was evaluated in the first part of this study. Increasing conductivity throughout the MDF panel may impart a better electrostatic attraction of powders to the surface of the composite. To retain and improve the fibre-matrix interfacial bonding in the presence of filler, Triacetin was used as a compatibiliser. Since the toxicity associated with urea-formaldehyde (UF) resins emissions is a growing health issue in MDF production as a binder [3], a soy bio-based resin was used as a suitable alternative.

As the relatively new resinous system consisted of three variables, their proportions may influence the properties of the panels. The resin, filler and compatibiliser contents were recorded in a full factorial design of experiments (3 factors at 2 levels) to establish their influence on mechanical properties and conductivity of the panels.

The second part of this study addresses how the manufacturing process of powder coating may affect the quality and the properties of the final coating. The first stage of powder coating process involves an extrusion process of all components of the formulation at temperatures around 100°C [4]. This melt-blending process allows thorough mixing of the resin binders and the crosslinker [5,6] and to avoid any premature chemical reactions and the curing of powders the extrusion has to be done at temperatures lower than the curing temperatures of 180-200°C. For low temperature curable powder coating [7,8,9], the targeted curing temperature is between 120°C-150°C leading to narrower temperature window between extrusion and curing [2]. Thus, understanding the synergy between extrusions and curing steps is crucial when developing new functional powders.

To assess how the extrusion stage may affect the curing behaviour of the extruded powder coating, the extrusion processing parameters were controlled [10] experimentally in a full factorial design of experiments (3 factors at 2 levels). DSC was used to determine correlations between extrusion processing parameters and curing behaviour [11] of a low temperature curable powder coating.

2. EXPERIMENTAL – PART 1: PROCESSING PARAMETERS FOR MDF

2.1 Manufacture of MDF and DoE

The manufacture of the MDF panels using fibres (Kenaf), a conducting filler, a bio-based resin (Soyad adhesive from Hercules) and Triacetin was done following a previously published method by Rao and co-workers [12]. The pre-pressed resinated mat of 24 - 26mm was transferred in a press with a metal spacer of 6mm to control the mat thickness at 120°C for 122 s, following a pressing profile (Table 1). The pressed boards were air-cooled, cut and sanded to produce samples for testing.

The resin (R), triacetin (T) and carbon black (C) content were varied according to a full factorial design of experiments (3 factors, 2 levels) shown in Table 2. Panels with two binders UF resin and Soyad adhesive with no triacetin or carbon black were used as control (Panels 9 and 10).

Distance (mm)	Time(s)	Total time (s)
9.3	30	30
8.7	5	35
7.2	30	65
6.2	10	75
5.8	122	197
100	2	
0	60	

Table 1 - Weverk pressing profile

Panel	Resin (R) %	Triacetin (T) %	Carbon Black (C) %
1	7	1	5
2	7	1	10
3	7	5	5
4	7	5	10
5	12	1	5
6	12	1	10
7	12	5	5
8	12	5	10
9	Soyad	-	-
10	UF resin	-	-

Table 2 - Design of experiments used for manufacture of composite boards

2.2. Material testing: Conductivity and mechanical properties

The conductivity of the MDF panels was measured in accordance to ASTM D4496 [13] on MDF panels measuring 70 x10x 6 mm. Commercially available “moderately conductive” materials are often manufactured in a manner that results in anisotropy of electrical conduction. Hence, the significance of tests using this test method depends upon the orientation of the specimen tested to the direction of the electric field. Significance and use of this test method is useful for the comparison of materials, as a quality control test, and for specification purposes. The conductivity on specimen from each sample was measured as mentioned in the test standard.

The internal bond strength was determined as per standard ASTM D1037[14]. The internal bond strength is the ultimate tensile strength perpendicular to the surface of the sample and is a common measure of mechanical performance of MDF panel. In conducting the experiment, four samples per panel of 50 x 50 cm size were flattened by sanding to within 0.1 mm and steel fixtures were bonded either side of the samples with hot melt glue. A tensile load with a crosshead speed of 0.48 mm/min was applied to each sample until failure occurred. Modulus of rupture (MOR) and modulus of elasticity (MOE) were determined in accordance with standard ASTM D1037[14]. The MOR and MOE are measures of the MDF board strength and stiffness in bending. Specimens of size 194 x 50 x 6 mm were tested in three-point bending scheme, a cross-head speed of 3 mm/min was used with a 1kN load cell until failure occurred.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION - PART 1

3.1 Conductivity - All compositions gave a statistically significant conductivity than the control panel with UF resin (panel 10). Interestingly, the panel with the bio-based resin (panel 9) without any

conducting fillers also showed higher conductivity than the control panel (Table 3, Figures 1, 2a-2c, 3a – 3b).

Figure 1-Statistical representation of factors contributing towards electrical conductivity

Panels	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
Mean Conductivity $\times 10^{-7}$ (S/cm)	2.96	3.14	3.54	2.50	1.82	1.98	2.13	1.20	2.02	0.44

Table 3 – Mean conductivity of panels

The resin content has a significant effect on the conductivity (Figure 2a - c). The Soyad resin used in this study is a proprietary adhesive hence it is not possible to correlate the influence of the resin in the panels under study in great detail.

Figure 2a -2c - Factor interactions for conductivity for a) R-T b) R-C c) T-C

Figure 3a

Figure 3b

Figure 3a - Main effect on factors contributing to Conductivity, generated via Minitab®

Figure 3b – Pareto charts of statistical significance of Main effects and Interactions contributing to Conductivity

Figure 3a and 3b show that the main effects T and C are not significant but there is a significant triacetin – carbon black (T-C) interaction on the conductivity measurements. The maximum conductivity of 3.5×10^{-7} S/cm measured on the panel 3 was higher than panel 9, the Soyad control panel (2.0×10^{-7} S/cm). Adding resin, triacetin and carbon black could in this case improve the conductivity of the Soyad panel by 75%.

3.2. Mechanical properties - Measurements of mechanical properties such as the internal bond strength, MOR and MOE for each panel are compiled in Table 4. However, the test of significance for internal bonding, modulus of rupture and modulus of elasticity showed no significance at the 95% confidence level for either main effects or interactions for resin, triacetin or carbon black.

Panels	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
IB (MPa)	0.42	0.21	0.23	0.14	0.83	0.64	0.49	0.67	0.08	0.18
MOE (MPa)	941	939	739	358	551	591	534	641	808	885
MOR (MPa)	8.20	6.25	4.95	1.98	9.03	7.23	5.88	6.88	6.9	5.5

Table 4 - Mechanical properties of each panel

The resin content shows an influence on the internal bond strength (Figure 4a). The maximum internal bond strength of 0.83 MPa (Panel 5) was with R at 12%, T at 1% and C at 5%. The addition of more carbon black and triacetin reduced the bond strength by 20%; IB of panel 8 with R, T, and C at 12%, 5%, 10% was 0.67 MPa. The Soyad and UF control panels at 7% resin were measured at 0.08 MPa and 0.18 MPa respectively (Figure 4a). The maximum MOE of 941 MPa occurred with R, T, C at 7%, 1% and 5% respectively (panel 1). The addition of carbon black and triacetin reduced the bond strength by 62%, for the same quantity of resin (panel 4 at 358 MPa). The Soyad and UF control panels at 7% resin were measured at 808 and 885 MPa respectively. An increase in resin and triacetin quantity increased MOE of panels (Figure 4b). The MOR results are similar to that of the MOE, with the resin and triacetin having a significant effect on the MOR.

Figure 4a

Figure 4b

Figure 4c

Figure 4a, 4b, 4c-Main effects on factors contributing to IB, MOE and MOR generated via Minitab[®]

4 EXPERIMENTAL – PART 2: DOE FOR PROCESSING PARAMETERS OF LOW TEMPERATURE (HYBRID) POWDER COATINGS

4.1 Extrusion stage and DoE - The hybrid powder coating prepared and studied in the present work was comprised of a carboxyl-terminated polyester resin and an epoxy resin with a polyester/epoxy weight ratio of 50/50 (Table 5). Components (Table 5) were dry blended and premixed for three minutes at 2400 rpm using a high-speed mixer. The premix was then melt-blended using a co-rotating twin-screw extruder, with 19 mm screws and a ratio L/D of 30/1. The screw design is composed of mixing and conveying elements (Figure 5).

Components	Specifications	Supplier	Wt (%)
<i>Carboxylic acid polyester resin</i>	Acid value 64-74mg KOH/g	Allnex	35
<i>Epoxy resin</i>	EEW - 700-900	Kukdo	35
<i>Pigment and Additives</i>	TiO ₂ , flow + anti-degassing agent	-	30

Table 5. Composition and specifications of powder coatings

The extrusion parameters (the temperature, the speed of the screws and the feeding rate) were varied according to a full factorial design of experiments (3 factors, 2 levels) shown in Table 6. The torque and the melt pressure at the die were recorded.

Figure 5 – Twin screw extruder

Extrudates were then cooled using standard methods using calendaring at 10°C and milling into powders prior to analysis.

Experiments	Temperature (°C)	Screws speed (rpm)	Feeding rate (g/min)
1	120	250	10
2	120	150	10
3	90	250	10
4	90	150	10
5	120	250	40
6	120	150	40
7	90	250	40
8	90	150	40

Table 6 - DoE used for extrusion of powder coatings

4.2 Rheology - The complex viscosity (η^*) of the coating was determined by dynamic rheological measurements using a TA AR 2000 Rheometer and was recorded (Figure 5) on dried pressed discs of powder coating placed between 25 mm parallel plates.

4.3 Differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) - A TA Discovery DSC was used to determine the glass transition (T_g) of the uncured and cured coatings along with the total reaction heat involved during curing. Samples (around 10mg) were placed in aluminium pans for testing. The settings of the thermal analysis are presented in Table 7.

Step	Comment
First heating ramp: 20°C/min from 30-80°C Cooling down:20°C /min to 25°C	Not shown in the Figure 6
Second heating ramp: 10°C /min to 200°C Cooling down: 20 °C /min to 25 °C	Determination of T_{g1} of the uncrosslinked system and the heat involved during curing
Third heating ramp: 10°C /min to 100°C	Determination of T_{g2} of the crosslinked system

Table 7. DSC program of cure

5 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

5.1 Extrusion - During extrusions, the torque and melt pressure at the die were two key parameters monitored (Table 8). There were no significant differences in melt pressure across extrusion trials. On the other hand, increasing the temperature from 90°C to 120°C lowered the torque. Torque values also decreased when increasing the screw speed from 150 rpm to 250 rpm.

Trial	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
Torque (%)	17	18	33	51	18	23	42	58
Melt pressure (bar)	2	2	3	3	2	2	3	3

Table 8. Monitoring of the torque and the melt pressure during extrusions

Melt viscosity of polymer systems is directly affected by extrusion conditions, such as the temperature of the barrel. Thus, powders extruded at 90°C have a higher complex viscosity than ones prepared at 120°C (Figure 6). At low temperature, resins were not softened enough which resulted in higher melt viscosity. During extrusion, when the viscosity of the powder coating increased, the torque also increased as more shear stress was required to move the screws into a material which applies resistance. Increasing screw speed improved the mixing but also raised melt temperatures by creating

local heating. Trials 4 and 8 (extruded at 90°C and 150 rpm), indicated the highest torque as their melt viscosity during extrusion was greater (Table 8). No trial gave an overload of the torque or of the melt pressure at the die, which means no formulations fully crosslinked during the extrusion stage.

Figure 6. Complex viscosity of powders extruded at 90°C (trial 7) and 120°C (trial 5)

5.2 DSC - All powder coatings exhibited similar DSC curves (Figure 7). The first heating ramp and cooling steps are not shown here for clarity purpose. Three transitions highlighted are the glass transitions of uncured (T_{g1}) and cured powder (T_{g2}) and the ΔH , the crosslinking exothermic heat. Table 6 summarises characteristic DSC values for the powders.

Figure 7. Typical DSC thermogram of the coating.

Dynamic DSC analysis showed that regardless of the extrusion parameters, all uncured powder had a T_{g1} above 40°C (Table 9), which is the lowest temperature required for the T_g of the powder coating before application that confers good physical stability to the stored product [10]. If the T_g is lower than storage temperature (40°C), mobility of chains allows undesirable particle agglomeration and can even lead to chemical instability in the long term.

Powder coating Trial	T_{g1} (°C)	T_{g2} (°C)	Reaction peak temperature (°C)	Heat of reaction ΔH (J/g)
1	55.1	76.2	156.6	17.84
2	55.1	74.6	157.0	18.04
3	53.8	77.3	156.6	19.83
4	50.9	76.5	156.8	19.09
5	53.1	76.6	155.7	20.87
6	53.4	76.1	155.9	21.31
7	52.3	75.7	155.8	22.36
8	53.8	76.0	156.0	19.83

Table 9. Characteristic points obtained from dynamic DSC scan

The reaction heat of a powder coating is related to its degree of chemical conversion α [15] and can be used to measure the extent of reaction. Therefore, if reactions have already partially started during extrusion, lower enthalpies for the coating are expected in DSC. However, in these trials, the extrusion processing parameters do not have an obvious effect on the heat of reaction as measured by DSC (Table 9). Powder coatings reactions usually have low exothermal heats involved when analysed by DSC and the insensitivity of the DSC for such low exotherms introduces more uncertainty in the DoE calculations.

The trends of DoE also indicates that at low extrusion temperature (90°C), the heat of reaction was higher than at 120°C (Figure 8) and the pre-reaction has started during the extrusion stage at 120°C leading to lower the enthalpy of reaction in DSC. Increasing the screw speed also led to pre-reaction during extrusion. When raising the screw speed, the shear forces caused by mixing were higher and created local heat triggering a chemical reaction. The feeding rate of the extruder also had a strong influence on the enthalpy of the reaction. When working at low feeding rate, more time is needed to fill the barrel entirely; therefore, the residence time of the material in the extruder is longer. Thus, the powder fed at lower rate remained for longer periods in the barrel at the same temperature. This triggered the reaction, giving a lower enthalpy of reaction during DSC analysis. However, except for the temperature, the test of significance for screw speed and feeding rate showed no significance at the 95% confidence level for either main effects or interactions for Screw speed and feeding rate (Figure 9).

Figure 8 - Main effects plot for ΔH , generated via Minitab®

Figure 9 - Pareto charts of statistical significance of Main effects and Interactions contributing to Temperature

CONCLUSIONS

Panels with 7% resin content, 1% triacetin and 5% carbon black exhibited the best overall properties. The addition of carbon black to the system influenced the conductivity of the panel drastically, with up to a 75% increase in conductivity. Lower levels of triacetin promoted higher fibre-matrix adhesion in the panel, resulting higher MOR and MOE but an adverse effect was observed at higher levels of compatibilisers in the panel. Higher resin content in the panels improved IB strength, but at the expense of reduced stiffness and electrical conductivity. However, when compared to the UF control specimen, all Kenaf fibre Soyad panels exhibited higher electrical conductivities making it highly suitable for powder coating.

In the study of processing parameters of powder coating, the barrel temperature, screw speed and feeding rates were the key adjustable extrusion parameters varied. Low temperature curable powder coatings are deliberately formulated for rapid curing and at a lower temperature than current powder coatings. Hence, they comprise highly reactive resins, crosslinkers and catalysts. The extrusion process needs to be tailored to fit those highly reactive systems. High extrusion temperature, high screw speed and high residence time may cause pre-reactions that reduce the chemical stability and the final characteristics and on the otherhand too low extrusion temperature could give inhomogeneous dispersion that could potentially result in poor film formation.

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